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Social Franchising: Multiple Pathways to Scaling Social Impact

Robert Newbery, Professor of Entrepreneurship, Northumbria University, UK

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Executive summary

Social franchising offers a powerful mechanism for scaling delivery of essential services to underserved populations while maintaining quality and sustainability. Our research in Kenya reveals that success follows distinct local pathways, not one universal template. Two factors proved critical across all pathways: accurate financial record-keeping and family support - yet development initiatives rarely prioritise either. These findings have implications for practitioners and policy makers in both developing economies and the UK/Europe, where social franchising can help scale delivery of healthcare, education, and community services. Context-sensitive programme design recognising multiple success routes is essential for maximising social impact.

Background

Social franchising combines social mission with business discipline to scale impact. From healthcare clinics to agricultural networks, the model replicates proven solutions while maintaining quality. In the UK and Europe, there is growing interest in applying social franchising principles to healthcare, employability services, and community-based social enterprises - particularly valuable where public services face budget constraints yet social needs remain high.

Despite growing investment, we lack robust evidence about what makes social franchises succeed in challenging environments. Most programmes assume a universal pathway, applying standardised models without adequate attention to local context. Our research analysed agricultural franchise outlets in Kenya, revealing distinct success pathways with lessons applicable to any underserved community (Newbery et al., 2024). While franchising has been recognised as valuable for scaling social ventures (Christensen et al., 2010), we lack understanding of the conditions under which franchisees succeed in environments characterised by institutional weaknesses and resource constraints.

Key Insights

Analysis of franchise performance patterns revealed both common success factors and context dependent pathways.

Social franchising enables scalable delivery through local ownership: Unlike direct NGO service delivery, franchising creates local entrepreneurs with ownership stakes. This combination of standardisation and local ownership effectively scales social impact across multiple sectors.

Success follows different pathways in different contexts: Our Kenya study identified three distinct success pathways, illustrating how context shapes what works: franchisees succeeding through business skills and market adaptation; through competence with strict compliance and family support; or through well-functioning markets compensating for lower skills via family backing. The key insight is that multiple routes exist depending on local context - undermining one-size-fits-all approaches.

Accurate reporting is critical but overlooked: Transparent record-keeping proved essential across all configurations, building franchisor trust. Yet programmes emphasise business training while neglecting basic accounting systems.

Family support outweighs community engagement: Family networks appeared in every successful configuration, providing labour and resilience. Community engagement proved unnecessary in two pathways, challenging conventional wisdom about community mobilisation.

Rigid standardisation undermines some franchisees: While reporting proved non-negotiable, operational compliance was not. Some franchisees succeeded through local adaptation. Overly prescriptive standards stifle entrepreneurial initiative in certain contexts.

Policy and practice recommendations

These findings point to practical shifts in how development agencies, social enterprises, and support organisations design and deliver social franchising programmes.

Avoid universal programmes for context-specific support: Assess local context (market access, infrastructure, family structures, skills) before programme design. Create differentiated packages matching local realities.

Integrate family welfare: Recognise the family unit as the entrepreneurial actor. Include partners and other family members in training and governance, not just the primary franchisee.

Prioritise financial transparency systems: Invest in simple accounting and reporting tools as foundational elements. Make transparent reporting non-negotiable while allowing operational flexibility.

Balance standardisation with adaptation: Mandate transparency while encouraging local operational adaptation. Focus standardisation on outcomes such as quality and satisfaction, not on the processes of how things are done.

Apply lessons to UK and European contexts: These insights are directly relevant where social franchises fill service gaps in disadvantaged communities. Social entrepreneurs, incubators and accelerators, and NGOs developing social franchise models should recognise multiple pathways rather than imposing uniform standards. Support mechanisms must allow for contextual variation.

Invest in comparative research: Examine whether these pathways appear across sectors and geographies. Study how franchisees move between pathways as contexts evolve.

Conclusion

Social franchising can scale social impact in underserved communities - from rural Kenya to disadvantaged UK neighbourhoods - when we recognise its inherent complexity. The evidence is clear: assess context first, then design differentiated support matching local pathways. By abandoning a one-size-fits-all approach, we unlock franchising's potential as a mechanism for delivering social goods across sectors and geographies.

References

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